

5-SHO‘BA TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

DEVELOPING READING SKILLS BY MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

Tojiboeva Mamlakat Begmurod qizi

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

Sheraliyeva Shoira To‘lqin qizi

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, student

Abstract: Literacy in the 21st century is about constructing and validating knowledge. This report explores how 15-year-old students are developing reading skills to navigate the technology-rich 21st century. It sheds light on potential ways to strengthen students’ capacity to navigate the new world of information. It highlights how countries need to redouble their efforts to combat emerging digital divides. It also explores what teachers can do to help students navigate ambiguity and manage complexity.

Key words: Readers, learn to manipulate letters and words in an interactive, multisensory environment, hypertexts and linear texts.

Introduction

It's no secret that children learn differently. Some need visual experiences. Others respond to auditory cues. Still others need hands-on familiarity. Some need all three. The same is true when children learn to read. Technology gives teachers exciting new ways to accommodate individual differences among students while motivating them to accomplish the difficult cognitive work involved in becoming phonemically aware and literate. Using appropriate technologies, children can see, hear and feel the concepts of reading and writing spring to life. Children are highly motivated as they learn to manipulate letters and words in an interactive, multisensory environment. Reading is a multi-sensory experience. According to research, the brain’s act of reading uses not just sight, but also the act of touch. There is something about holding a physical page of material that makes it more absorbable. “The shift from paper to screen doesn’t just change the way we navigate a piece of writing. It also influences the degree of attention we devote to it and the depth of our immersion in it.” (Carr 2011). Hypertexts are one of the web’s most important tools. Indeed, hypertexts are the reason that the web is called “the web.” The user jumps from one spot to another with the click of the mouse, and then to another, and then to another—forming a web of jumps. Often,

exactly where you are, and how you got there, may not be exactly clear. That's fine if you are just trying to continually refine your search for specific information.[1]

Materials and methods

However, hypertexts seem to be a major detractor when attempting to read a longer, cohesive text. “Research continues to show that people who read linear text comprehend more, remember more, and learn more than those who read text peppered with links.” (Carry 2011) As just one of many research examples, 35 adults were given a short story to read in the usual linear text format and were compared to another 35 adults who were given the same story to read in a version with hypertexts such as would be found on a web page. Even though the hypertext readers took longer, 3 out of 4 reported problems following the text, compared to just 1 out of 10 readers who were given the linear text.[5]

In addition to hypertexts, there is another feature of reading on the screen that makes it harder to find where you are while reading. Given a screen's ability to scroll, to alter the size of the text, to alter how many columns it presents, etc. (i.e., continually change what the reader sees), it is hard to form a reliable visualization of the material. You can't just say to yourself, “It was at the bottom of the left side of the page towards the back of the book,” because the next time you access the material, it may not be in the same spot visually. Long articles are not broken down into pages, further confounding the reader's sense of where she is in the piece. All of this matters, since “a good spatial mental representation of the physical layout of the text leads to better reading comprehension” (Greenfield 2015). The miniature screen on a smartphone only compounds the problem. Many people find it easier to flip through the pages of a book or printout than to relocate the spot on a screen. Technology is an integral part of almost every aspect of life today. While reading will always be an essential skill, a digital approach makes sense with today's mix of in-class, at-home, and hybrid learning.

Digital project work can help you connect learners to the books they read, better evaluate their comprehension, and build essential literacy skills like vocabulary, research, and fluency. Here are 5 reasons why integrating technology makes sense for your reading program.[2]

1. Digital learners need to be engaged

According to surveys by Common Sense Media, children today spend an average of 3-9 hours in front of a screen every day. While some of that may be using an reader, much of it is playing games and consuming video. Today's students expect to use technology, but that doesn't have to mean rote practice or simply consuming media. Make comprehension work engaging by asking students to practice reading and writing in real-world situations. Technology

helps by providing powerful tools, like Wuxia, that make it easy to create products like those they see in the world around them. Technology also makes it easy to share work with an audience beyond the classroom. Whether they are creating eBooks, comics, or public service announcements, when someone beyond their teacher views their work, students are motivated!

2. Technology can make informational text as exciting as fiction

Creativity is one of the hardest of the 4Cs to teach, yet innovation is essential to the modern economy. While reading fiction exposes students to an author's creativity, many educators find it harder to work creativity into informational text projects. Push your students to combine the knowledge they are learning with both analytical and creative thinking by changing the product or performance they create as a response to the information they are reading.

3. Technology is especially helpful in supporting English Language Learners

To build fluency in a second language, students must develop skills in listening, reading, writing, and speaking. Language acquisition expert Stephen Krashen suggests that true acquisition is, "an unconscious process when language is used for real communication purposes." We can encourage this process by giving students meaningful and authentic opportunities to both listen and produce language. Technology helps by making it easy to edit written work, engage with ideas and content in multiple modalities, and practice oral fluency without stress as they record, listen, and rerecord.

4. Standards demand it

New learning standards embed the need to conduct research and to produce and consume media into every aspect of today's curriculum! Standards also share the responsibility for teaching literacy with all disciplines, technology and media literacy should be a seamless part of language arts instruction. The themes, literature, and informational text in your reading program make it easy to connect reading to making.

5. Helps you bridge in-class and at-home learning

Many sites have already taken advantage of online tools so student can more easily move from an in-class to an remote learning environment. When students are already familiar learning in a digital approach in-class, the transition to home learning is seamless. Digital tools like Wuxia can be used across devices and anywhere students have an Internet connection. [3]

Today's creative digital tools don't need to distract students from reading and can help engage your learners more deeply in the literature and informational texts they are reading. You don't have to come up with instruction that combines reading and technology on your own. You can download these guides for unit-

specific technology project ideas for grades 1-6 themes like weather, animals, heroes, community, journeys, and discovery. Just because a teacher or school has technology available does not mean they are using it appropriately. When students passively play games or watch videos, they are not connecting and absorbing new information. During the coursework to obtain a master's degree in literacy, teachers will learn the many different ways students retain information. This may better prepare teachers for identifying effective technology for literacy development. Another common challenge in education is leaving technology out of instruction except for limited periods once per week or month. Students need to see technology as a tool to use when needed. Therefore, it needs to be available to students at all times. It is only through regular use that students will become literate.

Literacy development that includes technology can take various forms in educational settings. It can both support traditional literacies and introduce new forms in the classroom. Technology can help students discuss their ideas by bringing readers and writers together in the same classroom, and it can help students work together at different times through google documents and blogging. Another important feature of using technology is that it allows students to remix various media. The resulting product can be a combination of traditional writing and other new technology-driven genres. Technology is the bridge to creating a new form of education where the borders are undefined.[4]

Conculision

The last three months have been dedicated to exploring various aspects of the theme ‘Reading Comprehension’.

Learning to read and write wouldn't make sense if we aren't able to make meaning of what we read and write. But while there is a disproportionate emphasis on teaching students how to decode, hardly any time is dedicated to teaching children how to be active meaning-makers. As a result, it has been observed and emphasized repeatedly that lack of comprehension remains a dismal reality in Indian classrooms.

Our need to explore reading comprehension with practitioners, researchers and academicians arose from our deep discomfort with the lack of attention given to it within classrooms. One of the reasons behind poor comprehension is a lack of understanding of the processes and pedagogies that support comprehension among teachers. By exploring this theme, we hoped to build a shared understanding of a variety of processes and strategies that support stronger comprehension in readers.

The first set of blog pieces attempted to set the context for readers. The introductory piece (by Shuchi Sinha) described a range of factors that affect

reading comprehension, such as, decoding abilities, vocabulary knowledge, prior knowledge and the use of comprehension strategies. Elaborating on these ideas, Dr. Shobha Sinha from CIE, University of Delhi, described instructional practices important for developing engaged readers. Drawing upon both theory and practice, Dr. Sinha emphasized that comprehension is an interactive process, requiring readers to be actively involved with the text. She directed our attention to the role of factors such as appropriate text selection, good questioning and classroom discussions in meaning-making, while cautioning against the common practice of always ‘explaining’ things to children.

In the third blog piece, Shuchi Sinha summarized key ideas from Duke and Pearson’s (2009) much cited article, describing the nature of environments that support comprehension and key comprehension strategies that can be taught. Additionally, the piece goes on to suggest a number of activities that could support comprehension in classrooms.

No conversation on comprehension can ignore the presence of linguistic diversity in Indian classrooms and its implications on teaching and meaning-making. Dr. Shivani Nag from Ambedkar University described comprehension in multilingual settings in her piece. She wrote, “Comprehension of concepts cannot happen if the child remains alienated from the classroom transactions.” Her piece places emphasis on the inclusion of not just the child’s language, but also her culture and prior knowledge in the classroom.

Continuing the conversation on multilingual education, Dr. Giridhar Rao from Azim Premji University described four strategies that teachers could use to strengthen comprehension in classrooms where English is the second or third language.[6]

References:

1. Duke, N. K., & Pearson, P. D. (2009). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension. *Journal of education*, 189 (1-2), 107-122.
2. Fountas, I. C., & Pinnell, G. S. (2001). Supporting Readers and Writers: Tools That Make a Difference in Comprehending and Constructing Texts. In r. C. Fountas, & G. S. Pinnell, *Guiding Readers and Writers, Grades 3-6: Teaching Comprehension, Genre, and Content Literacy*. (pp. 440-460). Heinemann, 88 Post Road West, PO Box 5007, Westport, CT 06881
3. 21st-Century Readers Developing Literacy Skills in a Digital World
Published on May 04, 2021